

Title: Using Traditional East Asian Medicine Tongue Diagnosis to Monitor Physiological Changes in Individuals Undergoing Psilocybin Therapy

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Hypothesis : Psilocybin treatment will be associated with observable changes in the tongue according to Traditional East Asian Medicine (TEAM) diagnostic principles.

Study Purpose and Rationale:

- Personal and therapy assisted psilocybin usage has increased amongst the general population and Traditional East Asian Medicine (TEAM) patients. Although there is a copious amount of research regarding psilocybin use with biomedicine there is currently no published data through the lens East Asian Medicine. Data collected using the well-established and objective method of tongue diagnosis could potentially help practitioners better understand how psilocybin affects the body. This could be valuable to furthering the care of patients that are considering or are currently undergoing psilocybin therapy.
- Traditional East Asian Medicine (TEAM) tongue diagnosis is a non-invasive method to observe physiological changes that take place in the body. Due to its historical use in China for thousands of years, the measures are well defined and documented. This could be administered by taking photographs in a standardized manner that can be analyzed and quantified by licensed practitioners. While biomedicine has a lot of subjective data to contribute, they are limited in objective patient information.
- There are few effective treatments for patients suffering from PTSD or other psycho-emotional disorders that do not include a long list of potential side effects. East Asian Medicine has been shown to be a powerful adjunct therapy with little to no side effects and has been used to successfully treat both symptoms of PTSD and drug addiction (Tang, et. al., 2023). Collaborative research can mutually enrich our data which has the potential to enhance integrative care for patients.
- **Rationale:**
- **Traditional East Asian Medicine Assessment Approach:** Traditional East Asian Medicine offers a unique framework for understanding health and illness. Tongue diagnosis, a key component of TEAM diagnostics, provides insights into the overall health status of an individual by examining the color, shape, coating, and moisture of the tongue. Tongue diagnosis has been shown to be a cost-effective and easily administered diagnostic tool for use in the setting of gastric cancer, early-stage breast cancer, esophageal cancer, and other

diseases (Hans, et. al., 2016). The systems in which tongue diagnosis can be administered and analyzed has been widely researched and documented (Jung, et. al., 2012).

- **Complementary Diagnostic Tool:** Integrating TEAM tongue diagnosis with conventional medical assessments can provide a comprehensive understanding of the physiological changes induced by psilocybin therapy. While conventional medical tests focus primarily on biochemical markers and vital signs, TEAM offers a unique perspective that considers subtle imbalances in the body's energy systems as a whole. (Li, et. al, 2022). This can further the support from practitioners to their patients that are considering personal or therapy assisted treatment for their specific needs.
- **Objective Measurement of Physiological Changes:** By employing TEAM tongue diagnosis as a standardized tool, this study aims to objectively measure physiological changes, such as alterations in circulation, metabolism, and organ function, in individuals undergoing psilocybin therapy. The tongue serves as a visible indicator of internal health, reflecting systemic changes that may occur as a result of psilocybin's pharmacological effects.

- **Primary Aims**

- To observe tongue photographs captured before and after a psilocybin session to determine the influence that psilocybin may have on the body, based on TEAM diagnostic tongue assessment methods.

- **Secondary Aims**

- Integrate the TEAM understanding of psilocybin, and the changes we see clinically, with biomedical understanding to better understand the mechanisms of psilocybin in the body.

- **Tertiary Aims**

- Analyze collected data to ascertain the properties of psilocybin (ie. temperature, taste, actions, channels entered) from a TEAM perspective. This could have long term benefits to TEAM due to the increasing popularity of therapy assisted psilocybin treatments in our patient population.

- **Research Design & Methods**

- The parent trial will be conducted according to the guidelines established by the organization conducting psilocybin research (parent IRB#). Additionally, the SIEAM team will establish their parameters for collecting data. Data collection for this substudy includes a collection of 4 photographs per subject gathered before and after the psilocybin session.
- Pilot work has been completed to produce a system to photograph both the top and underside of the tongue in a controlled setting. Results from this inter-rater reliability of tongue diagnosis are below
 1. A study of EAM tongue diagnosis was completed to investigate the potential for multiple practitioners to have a high probability of discerning the same tongue qualities, referred to as inter-rater reliability.
 2. Five participants had their tongues photographed, taken on the top side when extended. The photographs that were taken did not have standardized lighting, distancing, or camera settings, were without a color correction card or computer application correction after.
 3. Multiple TEAM practitioners were asked to fill out a questionnaire and assess each tongue for their specific characteristics.
 4. Each question had multiple options, and participants were able to select more than one option. Additionally, participants had the ability to write in any additional information they felt important.
 5. Twenty-six TEAM practitioners and students took the test.
 6. Results showed that there were high levels of agreement amongst some characteristics, while others were mixed.
 7. This demonstrated that it is critical for the photographs in the parent study to be taken under a standardized and controlled environment, that the practitioners analyzing the photos have more than 5 years of clinical experience, and that the questions asked in the survey are as simplified as possible in order to obtain a high level of consensus.

With these results we can move forward to the protocol for the clinical substudy:

1. A Google Pixel phone with the capability to take 10 megapixel images will be linked directly with SIEAM's HIPPA compliant suite for uploading and managing photographs.
2. A single light source with a daylight balanced bulb (5500K) set on a tripod will be used directly overhead, at a 45 degree angle, directed down towards the tongue.
3. The area where the patient will stand will be clearly marked, and the lighting and camera will be on tripods, which will remain in a fixed area.
4. Each patient will have a QP Card QP101 Calibration Card near the tongue. Other features of the face will not be included in the photographed area. The calibration card will also include a numbered system in which we are able to track the before and after photographs of each patient.

5. Two photos of the tongue will be taken before and after treatment (one of the top of the tongue while it is extended and another of the underside of the tongue). A dedicated camera and lighting set-up will standardize the photos and decrease chances of operator error. Wherever the location of the parent study allows and is compliant with both parent and SIEAM study parameters, having a dedicated space that is set up with fixed locations for the participant, lighting and camera for the data collection in order to maintain consistency will be prioritized.
6. The before-photos will be taken within one hour before the psilocybin session. There will be a disclaimer to refrain from the consumption of anything that could stain the tongue that day (ie. coffee, colored juices, turmeric, we will make a list) and from brushing or scraping the tongue in any way. Another set of photos will be taken after the psilocybin session (sometime immediately after or up to an hour after treatment- to be determined).
7. The photos will be observed and coded by a licensed EAM provider. We have a code sheet vetted through multiple practitioners that we are still adjusting. The sheet will contain pictures to compare with in order to more clearly define the tongue body color, shape, and other relevant markers.

- **Consent Forms**

- Subjects who consent for the parent study will be asked to participate in this sub-study. Interested participants will be consented.
- Consenting patients sign a document which describes the time and activity requirements, and potential risks and benefits of participation in the study.

- **Preliminary instructions for patient**

- Patients will have to comply by signing a document illustrating following parameters to participate in the study:
 1. No eating or drinking colored foods or liquids (i.e. gatorade, turmeric, coffee, matcha, cough drop, etc.)
 2. No brushing of the tongue the day of participation.
 3. Nothing should be consumed other than water after the psilocybin treatment until the second set of photographs have been taken.

- **Eligibility Criterion**

- Anyone participating in the parent research

- **Exclusion Criteria**

- Parent study exclusions
- Those who do not wish to participate

- **Statistical Analysis**

- Statistical analysis will begin with utilizing what is known as the DELPHI method, which is a structured process for reaching consensus among a group of experts on a specific topic or problem (Schnyer et al., 2005). This would require us to gather a group of experienced acupuncturists to agree upon the question and hypothesis. Each member would be asked to independently assess the before and after photographs based on diagnostic criteria like tongue body color, tongue coat, moisture level, shape, etc. This would be followed by a group discussion of the findings which allows for knowledge sharing and consensus building among the team. The team will then independently re-evaluate the before and after photos based on the shared understanding. The revised evaluations will be combined and a statistical method will be used to find the average of the data to identify consensus changes in the tongue. This process can be repeated to further refine the data.
- Once the data has been refined and finalized, each characteristic will be coded by assigning a numerical value to each specific characteristic being evaluated. For example, tongue body color will be assigned a number correlating to which color was selected where 0 = normal pale red, 1 = pale, 2 = red, 3 = dark red, 4 = dusky.
- After the photographs have been coded and entered into the REDCap system, the statistical analysis can begin. We would be interested in tracking whether or not there was any change in the tongue when comparing the before and after photographs of each participant.
- The coded results will be used to calculate KAPPA, a statistical analysis method to measure the inter-rater agreement or consistency between two or more raters. This method quantifies the accuracy and level of agreement. It is a useful tool for evaluating the reliability and consistency of the data collection process, particularly when there are multiple options for each category (Jacobson et al., 2019).

- **Sample Size (N = 20)**

- Sample size is dependent on parent study. We will sample at least 20 participants.
 1. Participants have to agree to participate within the tongue diagnosis study.
 2. We are able to provide the incentive of either \$20 cash, or a free acupuncture treatment at the Seattle Institute of East Asian Medicine's Center for Integrated Care.

- **Safety Monitoring**

- We do not foresee any adverse effects from taking the tongue photographs.

- **Study Drugs or Devices:**

- A Google Pixel phone (7 or which model will take 10 MP images)
- A phone tripod
- A QP card for color correction
- A 5500K natural daylight bulb mounted on a tripod
- Masking tape

- **Outcomes Assessment Methods**

- We can now compare any potential changes in the tongues among the participants in the study in order to determine if there are trends.
- Will changes in the tongue be related to the qualities of the psilocybin? Further analysis would include whether or not any changes had a consistent theme, and apply such statistically significant outcomes to the potential actions of psilocybin within the TEAM context ie. flavor, temperature, channels entered. Currently there are about 400 herbs in the Chinese Materia Medica.
- Descriptive statistics will include: demographics, changes in symptom burden, along with tongue changes.

- **Confidentiality of Study Data**

- The photographs will only include the tongue, and no other distinguishing features.
- The patients will be assigned a number, so clinical information and identity information will be kept in separate spreadsheets.
- Only the participant's study number will be given to the people assessing and coding the tongue photographs.
- The use of a dedicated Google Pixel camera for the sole purpose of this study, linking with the HIPPA compliant Google Suite of SIEAM will minimize the amount of people able to see the photographs and keep them within a safe and secure system. Files will be kept in a password protected computer that only study staff can access.
- Informed consent . Patients will be consented for participation in the study.

- **Potential Risks**

- We do not anticipate any potential risks from someone participating in this assessment.

- **Potential Benefits**

- Increasing communication between Eastern and Western medicines and practitioners.
- To better understand the properties of psilocybin to be used in TEAM practices.
- Adding credibility to the TEAM diagnostic process.
- It is a non-invasive way of diagnosis, so could lead to (1) early prediction and (2) more frequent assessment, (3) cost savings.
- This could potentially be applied to the study of other psychoactive substances such as ayahuasca, LSD, MDMA, ketamine, etc.

- **Future Aims & Next Steps**

- To find an ongoing psilocybin study that would allow us to conduct this protocol alongside their research.
- To obtain funding from organization(s) interested in our study and outcomes.
- To further calibrate the tongue photos and survey using DELPHI methods to gather data that is more statistically significant.
- To find a small group of experienced TEAM providers willing to participate in the analysis of the final tongue photographs.
- Once this tongue diagnosis protocol is established and implemented it would be easy to apply to any other study involving a medical intervention where we would be interested in the effect that intervention has on the subject through the lens of TEAM.

- **Citations**

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